

Assessment of the Linear Source Approximation in THETA Transport Code for Deep-Penetration Shielding Problems

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803841

ABSTRACT

Recently, the random ray method (TRRM) has demonstrated considerable potential for neutron transport calculations. As a hybrid Monte Carlo (MC) and method of characteristics (MOC), TRRM still rely on the mesh discretization, which has significant effect on calculation accuracy. The conventional flat source approximation (FSA) has stringent requirements on mesh discretization, as it fundamentally assumes negligible variation of the physical quantity across a computational cell. Particularly, it faces challenge in deep-penetration shielding problems due to spatial discretization errors accumulation induced by steep flux gradients. We use TRRM based on linear source approximation (LSA) framework to better represent flux variation along each cell, thereby mitigating numerical discretization errors caused by strong flux variation. Results show that LSA scheme effectively balances accuracy and computational cost, showing robust performance across both 1D and 3D large-scale problems.

Keywords: The random ray method, Linear source approximation, Neutron transport equation

1. INTRODUCTION

As a fundamental aspect of nuclear engineering, radiation shielding calculations are essential for design and safe operation of reactor. High precision radiation shielding calculations are crucial for ensuring personnel protection and maintaining environmental dose rates within limits. Therefore, it have been widely researched and applied in the fields of particle accelerator [1], advanced reactor design [2] and medical radiation facilities [3,4] and so on.

In most practical engineering problems, neutronics radiation shielding calculations usually encounter the deep-penetration challenge due to the complexity of geometry and inherent heterogeneity of materials. Especially when neutron needs to pass through the shielding layer with a thickness much greater than its mean free path, the flux may undergoes a sharp reduction by several orders of magnitude. The key of radiation shielding simulation lies in solving neutron transport equation, for which the Monte Carlo (MC) method encounters severe limitations due to its prohibitively low computational efficiency in deep-penetration problem situation. Discrete ordinates S_N method the most commonly used deterministic method in shielding calculations, featuring high calculation accuracy and efficiency, and being suitable for solving deep-penetration problems. However, when dealing with strongly anisotropic problems, the S_N method suffers from the ray effect [5], seriously affecting the accuracy and reliability of the radiation shielding calculation.

Recently, a variant of method of characteristics (MOC), known as the random ray method (TRRM) has been developed for neutron transport calculation [6,7]. TRRM as the hybrid MC and MOC method, it treats the angle of ray as stochastic and perform batch sampling of characteristic rays. This approach

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effectively reduces the dependence on explicit angular discretization and memory overhead by leveraging statistical convergence over numerous ray samples. It is well-suited for solving three dimensional neutronics radiation and shielding problem with large scale [8–11]. Similar to the MOC method, TRRM still relies on spatial mesh discretization and adopt flat source approximation (FSA). Particularly in dealing with shielding problems where the neutron flux gradient varies significantly, the numerical discretization errors have significant effect on calculation accuracy and efficiency. A common approach to reduce numerical discretization errors is to employ finer meshes for calculation, whereas, the computational cost and memory consumption introduced by this refinement will increase sharply as the number of phase-space meshes increase. Linear source approximation (LSA) represents the source distribution as a linear function across the discretization mesh. This fundamental improvement considers the effect of gradient in transport calculation and allows using more coarser spatial mesh to achieve similar accuracy, which has been widely applied in MOC [12, 13]. To further enhance the fidelity of TRRM, the LSA theoretical framework based on TRRM is developed by Neame [14]. And this integrated approach has been validated in reactor eigenvalue calculation such as C5G7 and Babcock and Wilcox (B&W) core, demonstrating its improvements in both computational efficiency and solution accuracy. This work extends its application to the deep-penetration radiation shielding calculation. To addressing the critical challenge in shielding problems with deep-penetration and anisotropy, we use the LSA scheme to reduce the numerical discretization error in TRRM, thereby achieving higher computational accuracy while concurrently reducing the computational cost of simulations. By successfully adopting the LSA enhanced TRRM for shielding calculation, we demonstrate its versatility and accuracy in deep-penetration and large scale transport analysis.

The rest of the article is arranged as follows: In Section 2, we introduce the theory of linear source approximation in TRRM. In Section 3, we give the numerical results in two neutron transport benchmarks and verify effectiveness of the linear source approximation method. In Section 4, we summarize the main results obtained in this work.

2. THEORY AND METHOND

2.1. The Random Ray Method via Linear Source Approximation

The TRRM solves the transport equation along each characteristic tracking direction, and the differential form of the transport equation in current segment can be written as:

$$\frac{d\psi_{i,k}^g(s)}{ds} + \Sigma_{t,i}^g \psi_{i,k}^g(s) = q_{i,k}^g(s), \quad (1)$$

where $\psi_{i,k}^g$ is the angular flux along track k in mesh i and energy group g . In linear source approximation, we assume the source term varies linear in each mesh, which can be expressed as:

$$q_{i,k}^g(s) = \bar{q}_{i,k}^g(s) + \hat{q}_{i,k}^g(s - l_{i,k}/2), \quad (2)$$

here $l_{i,k}$ is the track segment length across the mesh i . In local coordinate system, the track-specific source coefficient $\bar{q}_{i,k}^g$ and $\hat{q}_{i,k}^g$ are given by [14]:

$$\bar{q}_{i,k}^g = q_i^g + [\vec{x}_{i,k}^c \cdot \vec{q}_i^g], \quad (3)$$

$$\hat{q}_{i,k}^g = [\vec{\Omega} \cdot \vec{q}_i^g], \quad (4)$$

where q_i^g and \vec{q}_i^g are the flat source component and the gradient of the source, respectively. $\vec{x}_{i,k}^c$ is the track segment centroids in local coordinate system. For the irregular regions, such as ring region, the

center point in local coordinate system can be calculated by using the length weighted sum of track centroids, i.e.,

$$\vec{X}_i^c = \frac{\sum_m \sum_k l_{i,k}^{(m)} \vec{X}_{i,k}^{(m)}}{\sum_m \sum_k l_{i,k}^{(m)}}, \quad (5)$$

where $l_{i,k}^{(m)}$ is the length of track k across cell i in iteration m , and $\vec{X}_{i,k}^{(m)}$ is the midpoint of track k in the global coordinate system.

In order to solve the transport equation with LS, we need to obtain the LS gradient which is governed by the LS spatial moments $Q_{v,i}^g$. Analogous to the case of the FS term, the update scheme for LS term depends on the scalar flux spatial moments $\hat{\phi}_{v,i}^g$, which can be written as:

$$Q_{v,i}^g = \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{\chi_i^g}{k_{eff}^g} \sum_{g'=1}^G \left[\nu \Sigma_{f,i}^{g'} \hat{\phi}_{v,i}^{g'} + \Sigma_{s,i}^{g' \rightarrow g} \hat{\phi}_{v,i}^{g'} \right], \quad \forall v \in (x, y, z). \quad (6)$$

Particularly, the relationship between scalar flux spatial moments and angular flux is defined as:

$$\phi_{v,i}^g = \frac{4\pi w}{V_i} \sum_k \int_0^{l_{i,k}} \psi_{i,k}^g(s) ds, \quad \forall v \in (x, y, z). \quad (7)$$

In case of giving the form of LS term expression, we can solve the angular flux $\psi_{i,k}^g(s)$ by the ordinary differential equations Eq. (1), which is given by:

$$\psi_{i,k}^g(s) = \psi_{i,k}^g(0) + \left[\frac{\hat{q}_{i,k}^g}{\Sigma_{t,i}^g} - \psi_{i,k}^g(0) \right] F_1(\tau^g) + \frac{\hat{q}_{i,k}^g}{2(\Sigma_{t,i}^g)^2} F_2(\tau^g), \quad (8)$$

where

$$F_1(\tau^g) = 1 - e^{-\tau^g}, \quad (9)$$

$$F_2(\tau^g) = 2[\tau^g - F_1(\tau^g)] - \tau^g F_1(\tau^g), \quad (10)$$

with optical depth is $\tau^g = s \Sigma_{t,i}^g$.

When getting the LS spatial moments $Q_{v,i}^g$, we can estimate the source gradients by spatial moment matrix \mathbf{M}_i as:

$$\vec{q}_i^g = \mathbf{M}_i^{-1} \vec{Q}_i^g \quad (11)$$

In local coordinate system, the spatial moment coefficient $M_{i,\nu\nu'}$ is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} M_{i,\nu\nu'} &= \sum_k w_k \int_0^{l_{i,k}} (v - v_i^c)(v' - v_i'^c) \\ &= \frac{w}{V_i} \sum_k l_{i,k} (v_{i,k}^c v_{i,k}'^c + \Omega_\nu \Omega_{\nu'} l_{i,k}^2 / 12), \\ &\forall (v, v') \in (x, y, z) \times (x', y', z') \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

At last, we obtain the final forms of LS gradients in transport equation about single characteristic. Compared to traditional FS approximation, it additionally considers the spatial moments of scalar flux, spatial moments of source term and local source spatial moment matrix \mathbf{M}_i , therefore the LS approximation method will have additional computational costs. Fortunately, LS approximation allows us to use more coarse mesh and fewer amounts of characteristics, which could reduce the calculation time significantly.

2.2. Three-Dimensional Particle Transport Code: THETA

THETA (Tracking-based Hybrid monte carlo-moc Efficient Tracking Application) is a three-dimensional particle transport code designed to enable practical, engineering-grade radiation shielding analysis using TRRM [11]. It streamlines the modeling workflow through automated geometry discretization, supports flexible cross-section and source definitions, and incorporates advanced physics models such as the LSA for improved accuracy on coarser meshes. The code features user-friendly XML input, integrated visualization capabilities, and a hybrid MPI/OpenMP parallel architecture to meet the computational demands of large-scale shielding problems.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

The performance of the LSA scheme in THETA is systematically examined in this section for deep-penetration shielding problems. The analysis aims to quantify the convergence of numerical accuracy with respect to the spatial discretization resolution.

3.1. 1D Deep-Penetration Slab Problem

To verify the performance of TRRM based on LSA in deep-penetration transport problem, a 1D slab benchmark problem was designed. It features a absorbing medium with a thickness of several tens of mean free paths. In this stringent case, any spatial discretization errors become pronounced in the deep-penetration region. The geometry and materials description are given in Fig. 1 and Table I, where the reflective condition was used in the left boundary.

Figure 1. (Color online) The geometric description of 1D slab transport problem.

Figure 2 compares the scalar flux profiles obtained from both FSA and LSA scheme. The results demonstrate a critical discrepancy in their dependence on spatial discretization. The conventional FSA requires an extremely fine mesh (0.1 cm) to converge. In contrast, the LSA scheme achieves comparable accuracy with the same mesh (0.1 cm), and maintains acceptable solution fidelity with coarser mesh (1 cm). This extremely reduces the dependence of fine mesh discretization, translates to substantially lower computational cost and memory usage, thereby establishing a foundation for the feasible extension of this method to large-scale 3D simulations.

Table I. The information of source strength and cross sections in 1D slab transport problem.

Region	Source strength ($\text{cm}^{-3} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$)	Σ_t (cm^{-1})	Σ_s (cm^{-1})
1	1	2.52866	2.51483
2	0	2.52866	2.51483
3	0	0.50683	0.50381
4	0	0.30744	0.30726

Figure 2. (Color online) The scalar flux distribution of 1D slab transport problem.

3.2. Kobayashi Benchmark

Kobayashi benchmark is a one-group, three-region vacuum fixed-source problem [15]. The one-eighth geometric model of this benchmark is shown in Fig. 3, utilizes reflective boundary conditions on the inner (axial) surfaces and a vacuum boundary condition on the outer surface. Region 2 is a vacuum medium, while regions 1 and 3 are composed of the same material, with region 1 containing a uniformly distributed fixed source. The source strength and cross sections are given in Table II.

Table II. The information of source strength and cross sections in Kobayashi-1 benchmark.

Region	Source strength ($\text{cm}^{-3} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$)	Σ_t (cm^{-1})	Σ_s (cm^{-1})
1	1	0.1	5×10^{-2}
2	0	1×10^{-4}	5×10^{-5}
3	0	0.1	5×10^{-2}

The flux calculation accuracy was evaluated along three distinct lines (A, B, and C) in Fig. 3. As shown in Fig 4, the comparison was performed using different mesh size conditions, with the calculated flux results by TRRM compared with the reference Multi-Group Monte Carlo (MGMC) method. In TRRM simulation, each batch tracked 1,000,000 characteristic rays, characterized by a dead zone of 300 cm and an active length of 2,000 cm. Meanwhile, a total of 1000 batches were run, with the first 100 batches designated as inactive batches. For the reference solution, 1000 batches with 50,000,000 particles per

Figure 3. (Color online) The geometric model of Kobayashi benchmark.

batch are adopted for MGMC calculation.

To systematically evaluate the efficacy of the TRRM based on LSA in strongly absorbing, large-scale shielding problems, a comparative analysis was conducted between the conventional FSA and LSA schemes. The computational performance of each scheme was assessed using both coarse (10 cm) and fine (1 cm) spatial discretization, thereby enabling a comprehensive investigation into their respective convergence behaviors and their ability to mitigate spatial discretization errors under computationally demanding conditions. It can be observed that when employing a fine 1 cm mesh, the flux calculation results from both the LSA and FSA schemes show excellent agreement with the MGMC calculation results in total region. However, a critical bias occurs in the deep-penetration regions: the LSA solution maintains its accuracy, while the FSA results begin to deviate from the reference. These bias arise from the failure to account for neutron flux gradients in FSA method, which allows numerical discretization errors to accumulate and propagate over long transport paths. In contrast, the LSA method successfully mitigates this issue, demonstrating its superior performance for problems involving large scale and strong absorption.

Furthermore, the prospects of TRRM lies in its error distribution. In general, MC solutions are plagued by high statistical variance in deep-penetration zones, whereas TRRM produces solutions with a relatively uniform and controllable spatial error. This uniform bias is inherently more manageable than the localized statistical fluctuations of MC, it depends primarily on the number of rays and simulation batches. This advantages allow TRRM to obtain the global convergence results with higher computational efficiency for shielding problems.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, this work has successfully implemented and validated LSA within the TRRM framework for solving deep-penetration radiation shielding problems. The scheme demonstrates a marked improvement in decrease spatial discretization errors, which are a critical source of inaccuracy in problems involving strong flux gradients and long transport paths. The numerical results showed that LSA effectively break the limitations of the conventional FSA approach, producing solutions that remain physically consistent with reference results even in deep-penetration regions. This scheme establishes a more reliable and numerically robust approach for shielding transport simulation. These results not only advance the calculation performance of TRRM in deep-penetration problems but also offer a promising methodology for high-accuracy radiation transport analysis in large-scale nuclear systems.

Figure 4. (Color online) Neutron flux distribution and relative errors along representative lines A-C. (a), (c), (e) represent the flux distribution along lines A, B and C. (b), (d), (f) is the flux relative bias compared to MGMC.

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